

Digital Echoes: Harnessing Social Media to Preserve Traditional Knowledge

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Traditional knowledge runs the risk of being forgotten or lost in an increasingly digital environment. The present paper intends to investigate social media as a potential tool for keeping traditional knowledge alive among the new generations. The study investigates how social media platforms can be used to record, preserve, and share cultural practices, rituals, languages, and oral traditions that have been passed down through the generations. Social media has the ability to sustain and revive traditional knowledge in a variety of global contexts by democratizing access to cultural knowledge and encouraging community interaction. The study also recognizes the difficulties and moral questions raised by this methodology, such as those pertaining to representation, ownership, and authenticity. The paper showcases creative approaches and effective efforts used by people, communities, and cultural organizations to harness the power of social media for heritage preservation. In the end, the paper emphasises that social media could be an important site for preserving and honouring the diverse range of human cultural expression for future generations if it is used intentionally and inclusively. For establishing the arguments the paper tries to bring examples from different aspects of traditional knowledge imbibed in the rich heritage of Assamese folkloric traditions.

Keywords: Traditional knowledge, Social media, Preservation, folklore, Community interaction